

A NEW ALGORITHM TO DESIGN OPTIMAL HIDDEN MARKOV MODELS

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ABSTRACT

A new algorithm for the design of Hidden Markov Models (HMM) from observed symbol and bisymbol probabilities is presented. The algorithm provides a global optimum and makes use of linear vectorial models of sequences of probabilistic vectors estimated during an off-line learning process. Moreover, a method to enhance observed data so as to comply with the constraints of HMM strings is proposed. An optimal estimate of the number of states of the HMM for the given observed data is also provided.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hidden Markov Models (HMM) are being used extensively as classifiers in pattern recognition related problems. They are usually treated as probabilistic entities and much of the developed theory and tools around them are inspired by the so-called stochastic analysis. This paper uses a different approach to represent them in a mathematically equivalent manner from where an efficient and fully deterministic algorithm for the design of a general HMM emerges. As a matter of fact an interesting alternative of their meaning based on linear vectorial models is already given in [8]. Though, the generality of the proposed algorithm to design a HMM in this first paper was seriously compromised by the severe constraints imposed to the transition matrix of the HMM. The aim of this paper is to generalise the algorithm in [8] and propose an alternative to the well-known Baum-Welch and Viterbi methods [3,4,5], by means of linear vectorial modelling. For this purpose an additional algorithm is proposed to transform the observed data so as to comply with the constraints of HMM generated strings. It enhances the observed probabilities of symbols and bisymbols (pairs of symbols) to remove unwanted perturbations. It also provides robust estimates for the optimal number of states of the HMM for the given corpus of observations.

Section 2 presents an overview of the HMM and the derivation of key formulas for the rest of the study. Section 3 discusses the derivation of vectorial models from experimental data. In Section 4 the algorithm to design a HMM with a general transition matrix is presented. Section 5 describes an algorithm to enhance the observed data. And finally, in Section 6 it is explained how the choice of the design parameters can be optimised.

2. DISCRETE HMM, AN ALTERNATIVE FORMULATION OF STATE AND SYMBOL PROBABILITIES

The definition of a HMM is given as,

$$\text{HMM}=(\mathbf{A},\mathbf{B},\pi) \quad (2.1)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_{(n \times n)}$ is the transition matrix of the n states model, $\mathbf{B}_{(m \times n)}$ is the symbol probability matrix and π is the vector of initial conditions. Furthermore $\mathbf{p}_s(k)$ and $\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k)$ stand for the state and symbol vector probabilities at location k respectively. It is shown in [8] that,

$$\mathbf{p}_s(k) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{p}_s(k-1) \quad (2.2)$$

and

$$\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k) = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{p}_s(k) \quad (2.3)$$

from where it can be deduced that,

$$\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k) = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}^{k-1}\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k-1) \quad (2.4)$$

The theory of linear vectorial models suggests that due to (2.2) the state probabilities may be expressed as a linear combination of sinusoids with frequencies and dampings determined by the eigenvalues of the transition matrix $\mathbf{A}$. In a similar manner the symbol probabilities can also be expressed as linear combinations of the same sinusoids with different weights, due to matrix $\mathbf{B}$, according to (2.3). It is therefore implicitly assumed by the HMM that the symbol probabilities of the observed data follow a sinusoidal distribution. However, in real life applications this is not the case and the problem turns into an optimisation process whereby one needs to determine the sinusoids which offer the best possible approximation to the probability distribution of the experimental data. It is the number of states of the HMM which determines the number of sinusoids used in the approximation. On the other hand the length of the string of symbols plays an important role in the accuracy of the derived model. It is shown that the sinusoidal behaviour of the probability distributions is not only limited to the state and symbol probabilities but it is extended to the n -gram probabilities [8]. The i^{th} component of the

m-dimensional vector of n-gram probabilities $\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k)_{(j_1, \dots, j_n)}$ is equal to the probability that symbols $\sigma_{j_1}, \sigma_{j_2}, \dots, \sigma_{j_n}$, appeared at locations k-1, k-2, ..., k-n respectively and the i^{th} symbol σ_i at location k.

In [8] the n-gram probability is given by,

$$\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k)_{(j_1, \dots, j_n)} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}_{j_1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}_{j_2} \dots \mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}_{j_n}\mathbf{A}^{(k-n-1)}\boldsymbol{\pi} \quad (2.5)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{D}_{j_y} = \text{diag}(b_{j_y1}, b_{j_y2}, \dots, b_{j_yn}) \quad (2.6)$$

and b_{j_yk} stands for the probability of symbol σ_{j_y} subject to state k. Equivalently,

$$\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k)_{(j_1, \dots, j_n)} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{A}^{(k-n-1)}\boldsymbol{\pi} \quad (2.7)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}_{j_1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}_{j_2} \dots \mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}_{j_n} \quad (2.8)$$

and finally it can be deduced that,

$$\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k)_{(j_1, \dots, j_n)} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k-1)_{(j_1, \dots, j_n)} \quad (2.9)$$

Note that the matrices $\mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{M}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{M}^{-1}$ share the same eigenvalues which implies that the probability distributions of the n-grams and that of the symbols are linear combinations of the same sinusoids. Training of the HMM consists in determining the distributions of the n-gram probabilities which in turn requires both, the accurate estimation of the eigenvalues of matrix $\mathbf{A}$ and the amplitudes and phases of the corresponding sinusoids. In [8] an algorithm to train a HMM is given which allows simple transitions from state n to state n+1. Here a new algorithm is presented which is applicable in the most general case where $\mathbf{A}$ has no particular structure. The HMM is designed based on experimental observations of the symbol and bisymbol probabilities which are estimated from the corpus of observations. The algorithm reaches a global optimum and it is inspired by the principles of linear vectorial modelling.

3. DERIVATION OF THE VECTORIAL MODELS OF SYMBOL AND BISYMBOL PROBABILITIES FROM EXPERIMENTAL DATA

Equations (2.4) and (2.9) imply that both the symbol and the bisymbol probabilities can be expressed by means of a first order linear vectorial model. In literature there exist a number of algorithms to train such models from experimental data. An interesting approach is presented in [2] and may be used to determine the parameters of the above models. For clarity, equations (2.4) and (2.9) are rewritten as follows,

$$\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k) = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k-1) \quad (3.1)$$

and,

$$\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k)_{(j_1)} = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{p}_\sigma(k-1)_{(j_1)} \quad (3.2)$$

with

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}^{-1} \quad (3.3)$$

and,

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}_{j_1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}_{j_1}^{-1}\mathbf{A}^{-1}\mathbf{B}^{-1} \quad (3.4)$$

Matrices $\mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{Y}$ can be estimated from observed data through a recently proposed optimization technique which makes use of the Cayley-Hamilton theorem [2]. More precisely, when equation (3.1) applies to experimental data an additional error term $\mathbf{e}(k)$ appears in its right hand side which is due to the existing noise in the estimates of the probabilities.

$$\mathbf{p}'_\sigma(k) = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{p}'_\sigma(k-1) + \mathbf{e}(k) \quad (3.5)$$

$$\mathbf{p}'_\sigma(k) = \mathbf{X}^k\mathbf{p}'_\sigma(0) + \mathbf{e}'(k) \quad (3.6)$$

where $\mathbf{p}'_\sigma(k)$ represents not exact but observed values of the symbol probabilities.

The Cayley-Hamilton theorem allows to write the characteristic polynomial equation of $\mathbf{X}_{m \times m}$ as follows,

$$\mathbf{X}^m + c_1\mathbf{X}^{m-1} + \dots + c_m\mathbf{I} = 0 \quad (3.7)$$

or equivalently,

$$\mathbf{X}^k + c_1\mathbf{X}^{k-1} + \dots + c_m\mathbf{X}^{k-m} = 0 \quad (3.8)$$

and by multiplying the above by $\mathbf{p}'_\sigma(0)$ and making use of (3.5) and (3.6) the following expression is obtained,

$$\mathbf{p}'_\sigma(k) + c_1\mathbf{p}'_\sigma(k-1) + \dots + c_m\mathbf{p}'_\sigma(k-m) = \mathbf{e}''(k) \quad (3.9)$$

This implies that the probabilities of all different symbols obey the same linear equation with coefficients directly related to the eigenvalues of matrix $\mathbf{X}$. First, the coefficients c_i , $i=1, \dots, m$ are determined by means of a least squares optimization approach and then the corresponding eigenvalues of $\mathbf{X}$ are computed. The latter represent the common frequencies and dampings which model optimally all the symbol probabilities. Based on these, the amplitudes and phases of the sinusoids are computed for each one of the symbol probabilities separately, as explained in [2]. Thus, not only the eigenvalues but the entire matrix $\mathbf{X}$ is estimated. In a similar manner one may proceed to estimate matrix $\mathbf{Y}$.

4. A GENERAL ALGORITHM FOR THE DESIGN OF A HMM

The algorithm of the previous section provides estimates for matrices $\mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{Y}$. Assuming that the transition matrix $\mathbf{A}$ can be diagonalized, the definition of $\mathbf{X}$ becomes,

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{U}^{-1} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{U}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{U}^{-1}\mathbf{B}^{-1} \quad (4.2)$$

Hence, by estimating $\mathbf{X}$ from observed data both $\mathbf{BU}$ and $\mathbf{A}$ become available too. Furthermore from the definition (3.4) of matrix $\mathbf{Y}$ it is clear that $\mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{Y}$ are similar which implies that they both share the same eigenvalues. Therefore $\mathbf{Y}$ can also be expressed as,

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}^{-1} \quad (4.3)$$

Note again that since $\mathbf{Y}$ can be estimated from observed data, matrix $\mathbf{V}$ may also become available. The combination of (4.1), (4.2) and (4.3) provides an alternative expression for $\mathbf{V}$ as,

$$\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{D}_1\mathbf{U} \quad (4.4)$$

or,

$$\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{U}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{U}^{-1}\mathbf{D}_1\mathbf{U} \quad (4.5)$$

or,

$$(\mathbf{B}\mathbf{U}\mathbf{A})\mathbf{U}^{-1} = \mathbf{U}^{-1}\mathbf{D}_1\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{Z} \quad (4.6)$$

Note that the product of matrices $(\mathbf{B}\mathbf{U}\mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{V}$ can be estimated since the values of the individual components $\mathbf{V}$, $\mathbf{A}$ and of the product $\mathbf{BU}$ are already available. Hence matrix $\mathbf{Z}$ is also available and by proceeding to its diagonalization, matrix $\mathbf{U}$ becomes available too. Finally $\mathbf{B}$ is deduced from the product $\mathbf{BU}$ and $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ from the initial condition $\mathbf{p}_\sigma(0) = \mathbf{B}\boldsymbol{\pi}$. An overview of the algorithm is given in Table 1.

Algorithm to evaluate the parameters of a HMM with a general transition matrix from observed data
1. Compute the probabilities of symbols and bisymbols from the observed data for all possible locations within each string of symbols.
2. Determine matrices $\mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{Y}$ from the first order vectorial models in (5).
3. Compute the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of $\mathbf{X}$ and $\mathbf{Y}$ as, $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{U}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{U}^{-1}\mathbf{B}^{-1}$ and $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{V}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}^{-1}$ and deduce matrices $\mathbf{V}$, $\mathbf{A}$ and the product $\mathbf{BU}$
4. Compute matrix $\mathbf{Z}$ as, $\mathbf{Z} = (\mathbf{B}\mathbf{U}\mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{V}$.
5. Compute the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of $\mathbf{Z}$ and deduce $\mathbf{U}$ from $\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{U}^{-1}\mathbf{D}_1\mathbf{U}$.
6. Use the product $\mathbf{BU}$ and matrix $\mathbf{U}$ to deduce matrix $\mathbf{B}$ and compute $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ from $\mathbf{P}_\sigma(0) = \mathbf{B}\boldsymbol{\pi}$.

Table1: Algorithmic steps for evaluating the parameters of a HMM with a general transition matrix from observed data

5. ENHANCING THE OBSERVED DATA FOR OPTIMAL DESIGN OF A HMM WITH A GENERAL TRANSITION MATRIX

The algorithm which is presented in Table 1 assumes implicitly that the observed data are noise free. It is only then that the probability distributions of symbols and bisymbols follow a sinusoidal law which is estimated accurately by the linear

vectorial modelling approach. If the observed probability distributions are contaminated by noise the performance of the above algorithm is compromised. Since in practice experimental data are always perturbed, a method is proposed to eliminate annoying perturbations before the algorithm of Table 1 is implemented. The enhancement algorithm is a generalized version of the 1-D technique which is presented in [1]. The generalized version appeared in [2] and applies to vectorial sequences of probabilities. It aims at reducing the rank of the individual channels of a sequence of probability vectors simultaneously in order to provide a perfect set of vectors which can be represented with no error by means of a linear vectorial model. Moreover the norm between the initial and the new set of vectors is minimized. The concept behind the algorithm is explained for the case of the symbol probabilities. It can be also used with bisymbols in a similar manner. First the p^{th} order global observation matrix $\mathbf{T}$ is built by concatenating the per-symbol observation matrices $\mathbf{S}_{\sigma_i}$, $i = 1, \dots, m$. Note that $\mathbf{S}_{\sigma_i}$ has the Hankel structure and represents the p^{th} order observation matrix of the sequence of probabilities $p_{\sigma}(k)$, $k=1, \dots, N$, with σ_i the i^{th} symbol and N the length of the strings of symbols

{ Matrix }

and,

$$\mathbf{T} = [\mathbf{S}_{\sigma_1}, \mathbf{S}_{\sigma_2}, \dots, \mathbf{S}_{\sigma_m}] \quad (5.2)$$

For the rest of the algorithm the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of matrix $\mathbf{T}$ is computed and truncated to rank n (number of states). This operation destroys the Hankel property of the submatrices $\mathbf{S}_{\sigma_i}$ which is restored through averaging along the anti-diagonals of $\mathbf{T}$ [2]. Thus a new set of symbol probabilities is obtained with improved (reduced) noise. This algorithm is implemented iteratively and converges to a global observation matrix of rank n , allowing a perfect fit of the probability distributions via linear vectorial models. Its convergence is guaranteed and in practice 3 to 5 iterations are sufficient [2]. Table 2 resumes the different steps of the procedure.

Algorithm to enhance the observed data for the design of a general HMM
1. Compute the probabilities of symbols from the observed data for all possible locations within each string of symbols.
2. Compute the global observation matrix $\mathbf{T}$
3. Compute the SVD of $\mathbf{T}$ and truncate up to n (number of states)
4. Reconstruct the new symbol probabilities
5. If converged goto 6, else goto 2
6. End

Table 2: Algorithmic steps to enhance the observed data for the design of a general HMM

6. SELECTION OF THE DESIGN PARAMETERS

In Section 3 it was explained that the design of the HMM from observed data is based on equations (2.4) and (2.9). Both estimates of symbol and bisymbol probabilities are required at different locations in the strings. Note that the derivation of the algorithm requires estimates of only one set of m bisymbols out of the m existing ones. It is therefore best to select the most frequent set in order to enable reliable estimates. On the other hand, the important issue of the choice of the number of states can be made from the observed data. As it has been shown both symbol and bisymbol probabilities follow sinusoidal laws with same frequencies and dampings. There exist as many sinusoidal components in these distributions as states in the HMM. An optimal choice for the number of states and/or sinusoidal components results from the effective rank of the combined global observation matrix $\mathbf{G}$,

$$\mathbf{G} = [\mathbf{T} \mathbf{T}_b] \quad (6.1)$$

where $\mathbf{T}$ is the global symbol observation matrix and $\mathbf{T}_b$ is the global bisymbol observation matrix. The number of significant singular values of $\mathbf{G}$ provides a good estimate for the number of states n . One way to determine it is by sorting them and simply observing their distribution. The location of a sudden disruption of the smooth evolution of their size provides a good estimate of the number of states n . Knowing n , the algorithm of Table 2 is applied to $\mathbf{G}$ to enhance the symbol and bisymbol probabilities. At each iteration of the algorithm the p - n lowest singular values of $\mathbf{G}$ are set to zero. In addition, at the end of each iteration the symbol and bisymbol probabilities are checked as to whether they exceed the limits 0 or 1. If they do so they are best reflected inside the interval $[0 \ 1]$ before the next iteration of the algorithm is performed. Initially the order p of matrix $\mathbf{G}$ is chosen equal to $N/2$, where N is the length of the strings. Once n has been determined, p can be set to a lower value, $n < p < N/2$. Note that the estimation of the best number of states is a self standing procedure and can be used independently to enhance the performance of all existing algorithms for HMM design.

7. CONCLUSION

The new algorithm for HMM design based on observed data provides a global optimum, allowing at the same time an accurate smoothing of the observed symbol and bisymbol probabilities. The algorithm is fast and makes use of the experimental data to rationally deduce an optimal value for the number of states of the HMM. This is used subsequently throughout the design process. It can also be used in conjunction with existing HMM design algorithms to enhance their performance.

8. REFERENCES

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